

EMERGING TRENDS IN HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM

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Abstract:

The hospitality and tourism industry has changed more than a little since the first motel, in San Luis Obispo, California, was opened in 1925. (Its rooms went for \$2.50 a night.) Today, there are more than four million guest rooms in the country, and tourists and businesspeople spend about \$550 billion each year on travel in the United States As a vast and growing industry, hospitality and tourism provides more opportunities for ambitious educated and uneducated persons who enjoy working with people. The hospitality and tourism industry working in a more competitive environment. It is essential that those seeking careers as successful professionals develop a strong business foundation and customer service skills. There are few main themes are to be required to promote the hospitality and tourism industry such as international tourism planning; the development and operation of hotels; Europe and the Single Market; planning issues and techniques; service improvement; finance and performance; and the psychology of management. The purpose of this study is to identify, analyze, and noted the future trends that has been done tat now related to hospitality and tourism sector. This kind of study will be helpful to identify both the advancement and some gaps in this field, thus help to establish a more efficient, effective, and accountable tourism research to support practical work.

Keywords:

Re-branding; Foreign tourists; Contemporary travelers; Tourism infrastructure; intra-national migration; Market travelers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Federation of Hotel and Restaurant Associations of India states that India currently has over 200,000 hotel rooms occupied across hotel categories and guest-houses and is still facing a shortfall of over 100,000 rooms. Leading hotel brands have pepped up their capital and are in various stages of commencement of new proprieties in India, both in metro and non- metro cities. According to World Travel & Tourism Council, by 2020, travel and tourism investment is estimated to should reach US\$ 109.3 billion or 7.7 per cent of total investment. The foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows in hotel and tourism sector during the period April 2000–March 2014 stood at US\$ 7,348.09 million, as per the data released by Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion. Foreign exchange earnings during January-June 2014 stood at US\$ 9.44 billion as compared to FEEs of US\$ 8.58 billion during the same period last year, registering a growth of 17.9 per cent. FEEs during June 2014 were US\$ 1.41billion.The number of tourists availing the tourist Visa on Arrival (VOA) scheme during January-June 2014 has recorded a growth of

28.1 percent. During the period, a total number of 11,953 VOAs have been issued as compared to 9,328 VOAs during the corresponding period of 2013. Throughout history, towns and cities have been a concentrate of tourist activity, providing accommodation, entertainment and other facilities for visitors. However, although much of the world's tourism activity occurs in urban areas from major cities like Paris and London to coastal resorts; it is only recently that urban tourism has been identified as a significant sector of tourism worthy enough for academic attention.

2. HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM IN THE WORLD SCENARIO

Today's travel and tourism industry has reached into a global economic segment with direct and indirect impact on the world economy. The International Hospitality and Tourism industry, which creates more than 258 million jobs worldwide and supports 9.1 per cent of global GDP. The activities contributed by hotels, airlines, tour operators, resort development, casinos, cruise ships, contract and event catering and visitor attractions..According to the report World Travel & Tourism Council, in 2012 was US\$1.2 trillion; 260 million jobs; US\$70 billion in investment and US\$1.2 trillion in exports .Along the way, in 2012, international tourism attracted 1 billion visitors globally for the first time in history and China became the world's largest spender in international tourism by spending US\$102 billion, surpassing Germany and the US. The sector has get advantage from the process of globalization and from the constantly falling relative costs of travel. In 1950 the travel industry recorded 25 million international tourist arrivals while there were 277 million in 1980, 438 million in 1990, 684 million in 2000, 904 million in 2007 and 922 million in 2008. Since 1990, international arrivals have increased by 4.3 per cent annually and the UNWTO expects them to rise by 4 per cent per annum over the next 20 years. In 2010, the sector's global economy will account for more than 235 million jobs, equivalent to about 8 per cent of the direct and indirect overall number of jobs, or one in every 12.3 jobs.¹⁷ The UNWTO is expecting the sector's global economy to provide 296 million jobs in 2019.

3. HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM IN THE INDIAN SCENARIO

The tourism and hospitality industry is one of the largest divisions under the services sector of the Indian economy. Tourism in India is a key growth driver and a important source of foreign exchange earnings. In India, the sector's direct contribution to gross domestic product (GDP) is expected to grow at 7.8 per cent per annum during the period 2013-2023. The total market size of the tourism and hospitality industry in India was at US\$ 117.7 billion in 2011 and is expected to touch US\$ 418.9 billion by 2022. The foreign direct investment inflows in hotel and tourism sector during the period April 2000–March 2014 was at US\$ 7,348.09 million, as per the data announced by Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion. According to a study conducted by SRI International ,India is plan to be number one for growth globally in the wellness tourism sector in the next five years, clocking over 25 per cent gains annually through 2017. The tourism sector in India is prosperous due to an increase in foreign tourist arrivals (FTA) and a larger number of Indians travelling to domestic destinations. According to statistics available with the

World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), income gained from domestic tourism rose by 5.1 per cent in 2013 and is anticipated to increase by 8.2 per cent in the present year. Hotels are also an extremely significant component of the tourism industry. The Indian hospitality sector has been growing at a cumulative annual growth rate of 15 per cent every year, adding required amount of foreign exchange to the economy. On part of the Indian government, which has provided policy and infrastructural support, has been instrumental in the promotion and development of the industry. The tourism policy of the government objective is to speed up the implementation of tourism projects, development of integrated tourism circuits, unique capacity building in the hospitality sector and new marketing strategies.

4. THE IMPACT TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY ON GDP

The major component of Gross Domestic Product is consumption, which is accrued by demand for goods and services. Tourism affects the economy through the provision of employment. The main effect of tourism on GDP is the fact that tourism improves the demand for goods and services. When ever increase in the consumption level, the market activity can also increased, and consequently, increases the GDP level. A part positive though, as it can also lead to leakages, especially in smaller areas. An area that has a high level of tourist-related activities generates a lot of employment opportunities for the local peoples. Hotels, amusement parks, tourist attractions and other such locations need people to provide the necessary services. Since increases and decreases in employment can impact the GDP levels by enforcing the spending habits of people, the employment provided through tourism has a positive effect on GDP. People who got the job have the income to spend and an increased level of consumption is a consequence of tourism on GDP. On the other hand –The Size and Economic Impact of the hospitality industry offer visitors from all over the world. Some of the choice of accommodation that offers are Apartments, Beach Houses, Holiday homes, Motels, Backpackers, Holiday Parks, Home stays, Nature retreats, Resorts, Health spas, Vineyard accommodation, Bed and breakfast, Farm stays, Hotels etc. Large number of international brands has entered the sector in recent times. The sector has been marked with increase in number of premium segment hotels in different parts of the country, along with smaller ones that cater the need for the middle class and lower middle class domestic tourists. Hence the industry can also provide employment to the peoples subsequently increase the GDP.

5. EMERGING TRENDS IN HOSPITALITY

The Indian hospitality industry has emerged as one of the key industries driving the growth of the services sector and, thereby, the Indian economy

5.1. PROMOTE F&B REVENUE

During the changed scenario has meant that many Hotels have started re working their strategy. One of the strategies adopted is pushing up revenues from F&B (Food & Beverage) as well as Banqueting functions. This has started paying dividends with some of the Hotels reporting increase in F& B revenue by 20 to 25% year on year. Going forward F&B revenues are likely to play a key role in the revenue stream of the Hotel.

5.2. PERVASIVE WELLNESS

Pervasive wellness support to rise to the development of new hotel patterns and other operations specializing in weight loss and total wellness designed to transform you during and after your stay.

5.3. HEALTH CAMPS

Health camps Signals broadens to include overall wellbeing, health as the centre of a holiday experience becomes more desirable. Hotel chains are re-branding around wellness, recognizing the concept and focusing on fitness .India's health and wellness tourism is expected to generate revenues of INR320bn in 2016, after increasing at a growth rate of 25.6% over the next 4 years.

5.4. SANCTUARY AND REFUGE :

Due to time pressures and an increasingly complex, interconnected world mean consumers search for more accessible places where they can escape and relax in safety away from the stresses of the day to day. Hotels will be provides a tech-free experience. Guests leave devices at the front desk and the in room entertainment is the fireplace.

5.5. ASSISTED LIVING

Hotels will become an increasingly attractive option for electronically assisted long-stay living as a buffer between the post-retirement and pre-nursing home life stages. People aged over 60 currently hold more than 50% of the wealth in developed societies would like to assisted living developed as a residential alternative to nursing home care option for seniors because of its emphasis on resident choice, dignity, independence and privacy.

5.6. TEMPORARY MIGRANTS

International and intra-national migration as many hope for better economic prospects. Seasonal workers, mainly in agriculture, continue to be the single most important group of temporary worker migrants .The ability to move globally continues, migration will increase exponentially driven partly by 'pull' factors (i.e. need for workers) and 'push' factors (i.e. civil unrest,

poverty). The migrants will require temporary medium-term accommodation in predictable locations. The Hotels will provide additional facilities to migrate for earning extra revenue.

5.7. MARKET TRAVELERS

The middle class in Asia and western countries are newly mobile and require accessible hotel accommodation for both work and leisure. By 2030 the global middle class will more than double in size, from 2bn today to around 5bn. International travel is still relatively young in China, it grow by 17% per year over the next decade . The role of virtual environments in our daily lives blurs with the physical and consumers cease to distinguish between these in the products and services that they consume.

5.8. REACTIVE ENVIRONMENTS

The proliferation of sensors, data and automation are creating reactive environments that can sense anything from weather patterns to user behavior, and automatically adapt the space and hospitality service experience .By 2020 the number of connected mobile devices is set to increase from 9 billion today to 24 billion.. Smart home technologies such as remote monitoring, light and heating control, motion detectors and cameras are all capable of being operated by smart phone.

5.9. MEGA-CITY LIVING

The more urbanization globally has been one of the most significant trends in population dynamics over the past century. The number of megacities is projected to increase to 37 in 2025, at which time they are expected to account for 13.6 per cent of the world urban population. The tremendous growth in urban populations will create thunder pressures on food, water, waste treatment, and health care, by 2025,

5.10. ARCTIC/ANTARCTIC TRIPS

The growth of Space Tourism, increasing interest and participation in Arctic/Antarctic trips, deep sea exploration and other remote journeys all drive more to seek to access the latest hospitality patterns. Space tourism, specifically suborbital space flights, could become a billion-dollar market within 20 years. The Advancing submersible vehicle technology increase access to deeper ocean depths, followed by more demand for hospitality industry

6. EMERGING TRENDS IN TOURISM

The following are emerging trends in *tourism* industry by adapting the service marketing approach for achieving great success.

6.1. SEDENTARY LIFESTYLE

It has been observed that contemporary travelers being bored by the sedentary lifestyle and mounting work pressure are yearning for leisurely activities and they are more eager in having new and unique experiences.

6.2. WILLING TO UTILIZE THEIR VACATIONS

Travelers are willing to utilize their vacations to the utmost to rejuvenate. Traditional travel sector which include adventure travel, nature tourism, cultural and heritage tourism and vacationing with family are still popular with the tourists.

6.3. THRILLING EXPERIENCES

Tourists are also admiring several non-traditional activities such as birding, mountain biking, cruise travel, festivals and special occasions, the thrilling experiences will offer splendid memories at tourism place

6.4. THE RISE OF E-TOURISM

The internet has modernized the face of travel industry, with its massive impact among the tourists. Travelers influencing their decision-making and is the fundamental force behind personalization and customization. Now a day they also prefer online bookings and reservations nowadays. These immense changes brought by technology to buy a standard tourist package proposed by a tour operator

6.5. EMERGING TRAVEL AGENCIES

Airlines, travel agencies and other travel professionals are merging with each other with the objective that bigger is better. Moreover, the growing competition among the airlines has resulted in opening up of new routes and most of the new routes to the US are more focused to the Western countries

6.6. POTENT ELDERLY PEOPLE

A large number of financially potent elderly people across the globe with enough time are looking forward to enjoy their dream vacations and are planning to travel

6.7. INBOUND DESTINATIONS

Eastern Europe, with many countries joining the EU, Asia and South America will play a major role as leading inbound destinations since they excite and arouse the interest of many travelers. We can predict that competitive advantage will be entered to develop and exploit.

6.8. *OUTBOUND MARKETS*

The biggest emerging outbound markets, we can cite here China and India with over a billion people each, many of which are starting to travel internationally for Improving their infrastructure, mainly road and airport and preparing communication media in relevant languages, which can very useful to attract the global tourists.

6.9. *SUSTAINABLE TOURISM*

The great demand and will continue its growth in the future since many travelers are now aware of the negative impact of tourism environment and have, therefore, become more responsible with regard to sustainability.

6.10. *NEW DESCRIBE ON GLOBAL WEATHER CHANGE*

Tourists thinking of about the planet, the erratic weather patterns and the natural disasters that will likely happened and are happening already. The travel agencies will gradually see new means of transport gaining ground to the detriment of air traffic, and tourists are willing to fly across the ocean if they consider the carbon footprint of their flights.

6.11. *NEW POLICIES FOR SAFETY AND SECURITY*

The tourism based countries are to be introduced new law enforcement agencies that protect both tourists and anti-social local practicers.

7. CONCLUSION

This analysis clearly highlights that destinations seeking to maintain or strengthen their position in the future world of Hospitality and tourism industry should start working on a long-term action plan comprising a set of strategies that comply in the future needs of the truism people. The above study deserves a deep reflex ion as it might spark other ideas and create interesting debates. Despite the size and complexity of the industry, today many of its arms are interconnected by technology. Computer systems now allow people to reserve airline tickets, rental cars, hotel rooms, and tours-all at the same time. These computer systems are called computer reservation systems or global distribution systems. Although many in the industry work in behind-the-scenes positions, those on the front lines-travel agents, front desk clerks, tour guides, and so on-must be enthusiastic and articulate. And in most any position, you'll need to have a love of service and a strong attention to detail. The Ministry of Tourism has been making

efforts to develop quality tourism infrastructure at tourist destinations and circuits in the country. It has sanctioned Rs 4,090.31 core (US\$ 680.52 million) for a total number of 1,226 tourism projects, which includes projects related to Product/Infrastructure Development for Destination and Circuits (PIDDC), Human Resource Development, Fairs and Festivals, and Adventure and Rural Tourism for infrastructure augmentation. In the On the other hand, natural disasters such as tsunamis, volcanic eruptions and earthquakes as well as health issues, such as avian and swine influenza, have changed our perception of holiday and leisure, other issues such as Market Segmentation and Overlapping Brands, Labor Shortages, Interactive Reservation Systems, and Globalization, are hurdles for the growth of hospitality, tourism industry.

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